

Pyridoyldipeptides and their Derivatives as Possible Tuberculostats Part IV. Isonicotinoyl and Picolinoyl derivatives

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DL-Methionyl-DL-methionine and DL-methionylglycine conjugates, their ethyl esters, hydrazides and a few 1,2-disubstituted hydrazine derivatives of pyridine-4- and pyridine-2-carboxylic acids have been prepared and tested for *in vitro* antituberculosis activity. Out of 29 compounds tested, 22 inhibited the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R₆₁ at 1 in 10,000 dilution.

In further pursuit of our efforts¹⁻³ to develop new antituberculosis drugs, DL-methionyl-DL-methionine and DL-methionylglycine conjugates of isonicotinic and picolinic acids and their esters, hydrazides and a few 1,2-disubstituted hydrazine derivatives (totalling 29 compounds) (vide Table I) were synthesised and screened for *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity.

N-Isonicotinoyl- and picolinoyldipeptide ethyl esters (1, 10, 12, 21) were obtained by condensation of DL-methionine conjugates⁴ of the corresponding pyridine carboxylic acids with ethyl esters of DL-methionine and glycine using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)⁵. The simultaneous formation of N-acyl-N,N'-dicyclohexylurea considerably lowered the yields of the N-pyridoyldipeptide esters. The esters (1, 12, 21) were converted to the hydrazides (3, 14, 23) by refluxing with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. However, treatment of N-isonicotinoyl-DL-methionylglycine ethyl ester (10) with hydrazine hydrate did not afford a solid product, although the infrared spectrum indicated formation of the hydrazide. The hydrazides (3, 14, 23) on condensation with different aldehydes, viz., *o*-, *m*- and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehydes and pyridine-2-, -3- and -4-aldehydes, gave the 1,2-disubstituted hydrazine derivatives (4-9, 15-20, 24-29). The N-pyridoyldipeptide esters were also saponified to get the corresponding acids (2, 11, 13, 22).*

EXPERIMENTAL*

N-Pyridoyldipeptide ethyl esters (1, 10, 12, 21)

General Procedure : N-Pyridoyl-DL-methionine (0.02 mole) and DL-methionine/glycine ethyl ester (0.03 mole) were condensed in dry dimethylformamide (DMF) for compounds

1. K. U. M. Prasad, B. H. Iyer and M. Sirsi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 9.
2. K. U. M. Prasad, B. H. Iyer and M. Sirsi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 784.
3. K. U. M. Prasad, B. H. Iyer and M. Sirsi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **32**, 181.

*Melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra of all the compounds taken in nujol mull using a Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model 137B showed characteristic absorptions. Melting points, yields and analyses of all the compounds are listed in Table I.

4. S. N. Nigam, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University (1959).
5. J. C. Sheehan and G. P. Hess, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1067; H. G. Khorana, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1955, 1087.

TABLE I

Pyridoyldipeptides and their derivatives

Compound	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. (°C)	Yield (%)	Formula	Analysis ^a
<i>Isonicotinoyl series</i>						
1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ SCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	111-112	36	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	C, H, N
2	..	OH	213-215	47	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	N
3	..	NHNH ₂	198-199	78	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	C, H, N
4	..	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	205-207	—	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	N
5	..	..	(m) 229-231	—	..	C, H, N
6	..	..	(p) 241-242	—	..	C, H, N
7	..	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ N (α)	237-239	—	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	C, H, N
8	..	..	(β) 208-213	—	..	C, H, N
9	..	..	(γ) 208-210	—	..	N
10	H	OC ₂ H ₅	118-120	41	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	C, H, N
11	H	OH	215-216(d)	55	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	N
<i>Picolinoyl series</i>						
12	CH ₂ CH ₂ SCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	112-113	30	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	C, H, N
13	..	OH	145-147	67	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	N
14	..	NHNH ₂	142-145	39	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	C, H, N
15	..	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	160-162	—	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	C, H, N
16	..	..	(m) 207.5-209	—	..	C, H, N
17	..	..	(p) 196-198	—	..	C, H, N
18	..	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ N (α)	161-162	—	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	C, H, N
19	..	..	(β) 181-182	—	..	C, H, N
20	..	..	(γ) 152-153	—	..	N
21	H	OC ₂ H ₅	86-88	35	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	C, H, N
22	H	OH	148-154	76	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	N
23	H	NHNH ₂	145-147	87	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	C, H, N
24	H	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	146-150	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₅ S	C, H, N
25	H	..	(m) 165	—	..	C, H, N
26	H	..	(p) 204-205	—	..	C, H, N
27	H	NHN = CHC ₆ H ₄ N (α)	132-134	—	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S	N
28	H	..	(β) 169-172	—	..	N
29	H	..	(γ) 157-158	—	..	N

^a Analytical results for indicated elements are within ±0.5% of the theoretical values.

1 and 10 and dry dioxan for 12 and 21 using DCC (0.02 mole). When DMF was used as solvent, the reaction mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture (ice-salt) during the addition of DCC and then it was kept at about -5° for 2 days before working up. With dioxan as solvent, the reaction mixture was cooled in ice and water during the addition of DCC and then stirred at room temperature for 24 hours. After decomposing the excess DCC with acetic acid, the *N,N'*-dicyclohexylurea was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The residue was taken up in ethyl acetate, washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated and allowed to stand. The crystallised *N*-pyridoyl-*N,N'*-dicyclohexylurea (*viz.*, *N*-Isonicotinoyl *N,N'*-dicyclohexylurea—m.p. 164–166°; Anal. Found : N, 12.62. $C_{24}H_{36}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 12.17% or *N*-picolinoyl-*N,N'*-dicyclohexylurea—m.p. 167–168°; Anal. Found : N, 12.54. $C_{24}H_{36}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 12.17%) was removed by filtration. Addition of petroleum ether to the filtrate furnished the crude dipeptide ester which was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether.

N-Pyridoyldipeptide hydrazides (3, 14, 23)

General Procedure : A mixture of the ester (1, 12 or 21) (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (0.04–0.1 mole) in ethanol was refluxed for 6–10 hours. The solvent and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed *in vacuo* and the residue crystallised from ethanol.

1,2-Disubstituted hydrazine derivatives (4–9, 15–20, 24–29)

General Procedure : A mixture of the hydrazide (3, 14 or 23) (1 g) and an equimolar quantity of the aldehyde in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 10 hours. On concentrating the solution and cooling, the product crystallised. It was recrystallised from ethanol or aqueous ethanol.

N-Pyridoyldipeptide acids (2, 11, 13, 22)

General Procedure : The ester (1, 10, 12 or 21) (0.005 mole) was stirred with 1*N* sodium hydroxide (0.01 mole) at room temperature for 6 hours. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate acidified with 1*N* hydrochloric acid to pH 3–3.5. The precipitated solid was crystallised from ethanol.

Pharmacological activity : All the 29 compounds were tested for *in vitro* antituberculosis activity by surface culture technique using the virulent human strain *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v. Except the compounds 9, 10, 11, 13, 19, 28 and 29, rest of them inhibited the growth of the organism at 1 in 10,000 dilution.

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